

**THE ARCUATE NUCLEUS OF THE HYPOTHALAMUS IN THE
POST-INTENSIVE CARE PERIOD AFTER 10 MINUTES OF CLINICAL
DEATH**

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Abstract The mechanism of development of post-intensive care disease remains one of the urgent problems of intensive care in the world. The stress reaction that occurs in the body under the influence of extreme factors is not a separate process. First of all, this process is ensured by individual adaptation at the level of the autonomous nervous and neuroendocrine systems of the body. At the same time, in the post-intensive care period, changes in the relationship of hormones of the reproductive system remain a little-studied problem of modern fundamental and clinical medicine. The object of the study was 80 mongrel, white, sexually mature female rats with a weight of 160-180 g., in which the state of clinical death and post-resuscitation disease was modeled according to the method of V.G.Korpachev (1982). The relationship of morphofunctional changes in the NSC of the hypothalamus ARYA with the reactivity of the ANS during clinical death and I-II-III-IV-V stages and long-term periods (1 and 3 months) of post-intensive care disease was determined when modeling 10-minute clinical death.

In the early I-II stages of post-intensive care disease, against the background

of the predominance of PSNS reactivity and an increase in destructively altered NSCs in the form of karyolysis, plasmolysis, there is an increase in the morphofunctional activity of ARYA NSCs. Coming to the III stage of post-resuscitation disease against the background of the predominance of the tone of the SNC and the connection of the trophic function of glial satellite cells, the morphofunctional activity of the NSC ARYA is at the stage of maximum functional activity Starting from the IV stage, as well as V- at the stage and in the long-term periods of post-resuscitation disease, against the background of the predominance of SNS tone, an increase in the activity of glial satellite cells, vicarious compensation of NSCs and an increase in the number of destructively altered NSCs, the recovery process is noted, as the duration of post-resuscitation disease lengthens, the recovery process deepens.

Keywords. Clinical death, post-intensive care disease, autonomic nervous system, hypothalamus, arquatic nucleus

Introduction. Currently, an expanded and in-depth study of the mechanisms of development of post-resuscitation disease remains one of the important problems of resuscitators [1,2,3,4]. In the process of dying and in the post-intensive care period, a deep imbalance occurs in the body between the anabolic and catabolic processes of the body. At the same time, the naturally occurring process under the action of extreme factors on the body is not an independent phenomenon; From the very beginning, it is realized as a necessary link in the individual adaptation of the body to the hypothalamic-pituitary system with the activation of adaptogenic hormones [17,25,23,22].. With excessive force or complexity of the environmental impact, adaptation may not be feasible. Such is clinical death [10]. Clinical death in the post-intensive care period necessarily affects the functional and trophic properties of cells of body systems

[5,6,9,14,15,16,21]. In this case, stress, hypoxia and reoxygenation are inevitably combined, as well as hemolytic anemia [18,19,20],

in which there is an alteration of cellular structures[18], and the productive state remains at a disadvantage. One of the main centers responsible for the productive state of the body's cells is the hypothalamic – adenohipophysial system – the neurosecretory cells (NSC) of the arcuate nucleus (ARA) of the hypothalamus [24,7,] and the autonomic nervous system (ANS) of the body [1]. Without knowledge of the dynamics and sequence of changes occurring in this system, it is difficult to imagine the mechanisms of development of post-intensive care disease.

The purpose of the study. To identify the relationship of morphofunctional changes in the NSC of the hypothalamus ARYA with the reactivity of the ANS I-II-III-IV-V stages and long-term periods (1 and 3 months) of post-resuscitation disease in modeling 10-minute clinical death.

Materials and methods of research. In connection with the task, a study was conducted on 80 mongrel male rats weighing 130-220 gy, in which the state of clinical death was simulated [8] The reactivity of the ANS was determined by the Hildebrant coefficient [1]. Histochemical, cytophotometric, and morphometric methods were used for morphofunctional activity of hypothalamic nuclei.

The functional activity of NSCs and basophilic cells of the adenohipophysis (high, moderate and low activity) was determined by criteria for the content of HCV and glycoprotein, the volume of nuclei, nucleoli, the state of the nucleolus and chromatin in the nucleus of NSCs and basophilic cells of the pituitary gland, which includes calculating the percentage of individual types of NSCs. The functional character of the nuclei was assessed using the nuclear–cytoplasmic ratio index. $\text{Index} = \text{Volume of the nucleus} / \text{volume of the cytoplasm}$. An increase in the index indicates an increase in genetic activity and hydration of cell nuclei. A decrease in the index indicates the hydration of the

cytoplasm and a decrease in the genetic activity of cell nuclei [12,13].

Stat processing was performed using the standard Microsoft Office software package – Excel 2000.

The results of the study and their discussion. In the study of intact animals against the background of mixed reactivity, the ANS NSCs are at the stage of moderate functional activity, while NSCs of moderate functional activity are $68.0 \pm 0.5\%$, and NSCs of high and low functional activity are $11.8 \pm 0.7\%$ and $15.0 \pm 0.5\%$, destructive NSCs of up to 5.2 ± 0.4 are found between these cells% (hyperchromic pycnotic cells). Their nuclei are hyperchromic, the chromatin in them is diffusely located throughout the nucleus, the nucleolus is located mainly in the center of the nucleus. The nuclear cytoplasmic index is 0.227 ± 0.0006 . The nuclei of glial satellite cells are also chromatic, the area varies within 14.2 ± 0.3 units. The capillary network is slightly hyperemic, the diameter of the capillaries is 5.8 ± 0.05 microns.

After the onset of clinical death on the background of vagotonia after 10 minutes, the NSCs are slightly swollen, there are some decreases in the intensity of NSV in the cytoplasm of cells. The nucleus is chromatic, the chromatin in them, as in intact animals, is diffusely located throughout the nucleus. There is a decrease in the number of NSCs of low functional activity, respectively, with an increase in the number of NSCs of high functional activity, but the indicators are insignificant ($P > 0.05$).

In the early post-intensive care period (I-II stages of post-intensive care disease), against the background of maintaining the reactivity of the ANS, the tone of the parasympathetic nervous system (PSNS), there was a further increase in NSCs of high functional activity - $37.4 \pm 0.8\%$ ($P < 0.001$) with a decrease in the number of NSCs of moderate and low functional activity to $49.4 \pm 1.4\%$ and $6.8 \pm 0.6\%$ ($P < 0.001$), while the index of the nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio was reduced to 0.223 ± 0.0005 ($P < 0.01$). Coming to the second stage of post-intensive

care disease, there is an increase in the number of destructively altered NSCs in the form of cytolysis to $6.4 \pm 1.9\%$, but the indicators are insignificant ($P > 0.05$). Сосудистая сеть в области АРЯ гиперемирована, отмечается выраженный периваскулярный отек, диаметр капилляров увеличен до $6,4 \pm 0,1$ мкм ($P < 0,05$).

Coming to the III stage of post-resuscitation disease against the background of the predominance of SNC tone in the reactivity of the ANS, the severity of hyperemia of the capillary network against the background of perivascular edema, as well as an increase in the functional activity of glial cells- satellites in the form of cytoplasmic vacuolation and with an increase in the area of nuclei with two nucleoli to 18.0 ± 0.2 cu ($P < 0.001$), there is a sharp increase in the number of NSCs of high functional activity by hypertrophied nuclei with eccentrically located nucleoli to $66.0 \pm 1.3\%$ ($P < 0.001$), with a decrease in the number of NSCs of moderate and low functional activity up to $20.4 \pm 1.3\%$ ($P < 0.001$) and $5.4 \pm 0.2\%$ ($P < 0.001$), an increase in the nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio index to 0.229 ± 0.004 ($P < 0.05$) is noted. At the same time, there is a lag in the synthesis of HCV from its secretion and a further increase in the number of destructively altered NSCs in the form of karyolysis and cytolysis to $8.0 \pm 0.4\%$ ($P < 0.01$) with a shift towards depletion

Recovery processes, starting from stage IV, during stage V and long-term periods (1-3 months) of post-resuscitation disease against the background of predominance of SNA reactivity, hyperemia of the capillary network with the manifestation of perivascular edema and a further increase in the area of the nuclei of glial satellite cells to 18.5 ± 0.2 units ($P < 0.001$), when connected vicarious compensation of NSCs with two nucleoli, as well as with an increase in the number of destructively altered NSCs to $8.2 \pm 0.4\%$ ($P < 0.001$), There was an increase in the number of NSCs of moderate functional activity to $36.8 \pm 0.5\%$ ($P < 0.001$) with an increase in chromatin in the nucleus, that is, there was a

restoration of morphofunctional activity of NSCs of the hypothalamus ARYA.

As the duration of the period of post-intensive care disease lengthens, these processes are significantly delayed. That is, against the background of maintaining the reactivity of the SNA, there is an increase in the number of destructively altered NSCs of a hyperchromic-pyknotic nature.

Therefore, if we interpret the data obtained in the early post-resuscitation period (I-II stages of the disease) against the background of predominance of PSNS tone, hyperemia of the capillary network with pronounced perivascular edema, a decrease in the index of the nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio, we can talk about hyperhydration of the cytoplasm during the passive phase of functional activity of the nuclei of the NSC ARYA [12].

As for what we found in the III-IV-V stages and long-term periods of post-resuscitation disease against the background of predominance of reactivity, an increase in the NSC ARYA in high functional activity and the index of the nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio, an increase in the number of two nucleolar cells - in later periods of resuscitation, and chromatin, this can be interpreted as one of the additional mechanisms of compensatory processes, since the latter is an indicator of the activation of the genetic apparatus in them [11,12]. If these data are interpreted with Zavodovsky's data, then the basis for the development of post-resuscitation disease is the lack of peptide neurohormones of the NSC ARYA responsible for the productive state of the body.

Thus, based on the data obtained, the following can be done vsvods:

1. After the onset of clinical death on the background of vagotonia, after 10 minutes, there is a slight increase in the morphofunctional activity of the NSC ARYA
2. In the early I-II stages of post-resuscitation disease, against the background of the predominance of PSNS reactivity and an increase in destructively altered NSCs in the form of karyolysis, plasmolysis, there is an increase in the

morphofunctional activity of ARYA NSCs.

3. In the III stage of post-resuscitation disease, against the background of the predominance of the tone of the CHS and the connection of the trophic function of glial satellite cells in the form of cytoplasm vacuolization and an increase in the area of nuclei, the morphofunctional activity of NSC ARYA is at the stage of maximum functional activity with a lag in the synthesis of HCV from its secretion with a shift towards depletion.

4. Starting from the IV stage, as well as the V stage and in the long-term periods of post-intensive care disease against the background of predominance of the tone of the SNS, an increase in the area

glial satellite cells with two nucleoli, vicarious compensation of NSCs and an increase in the number of destructively altered NSCs, the recovery process is noted, as the duration of post-intensive care disease lengthens, the recovery process deepens.

Literature

1. Вейна А. М. Заболевания вегетативной нервной системы // Руководство М.: Медицина 1991. - 624 с.
2. Волков А. В. Влияние гормонов на процессы восстановления после клинической смерти в эксперименте. // Патологическая физиология и экспериментальная терапия. терапия 1987; (3): 27—30.
3. Волков А. В., Аврущенко М. Ш., Горенкова Н. А., Заржецкий Ю. В. Значение полового диморфизма и репродуктивных гормонов в патогенезе и исходе постреанимационной болезни. // Общая реаниматология 2006; 2 (5—6): 70—78.

4. Волков А.В., Мороз В.В., Ежова К.Н., Заржецкий Ю.В. Роль половых стероидов в восстановительном периоде после клинической смерти (экспериментальное исследование). Общая реаниматология.- 2010. 4(1):-С.1-18
5. Горизонтов П.Д. Стресс и система крови / П. Д. Горизонтов, О .И. Белоусова, М.И. Федотова. - М.: Медицина, АМН СССР, 1983. -240 с.
6. Заречнова Н.Н., Слынько Т.Н. Влияние горной гипоксии на органы эндокринной системы при недостаточности гормонов надпочечника и поджелудочной железы. // Вестник новых медицинских технологий. Электронное издание 2018;(4):3-10.
7. Ковалева Ю.О. Анализ участия женского полового гормона эстрадиола в развитии гипоксической формы легочной гипертензии у самок крыс.//Автореферат диссертации. Москва 2014: 24с.
8. Корпачев В. Г., Лысенков С. П., Тель Л. З. Моделирование клинической смерти и постреанимационной болезни у крыс. Патологическая физиология и экспериментальная терапия 1982;(3): 78—80.
9. Кубасов Р.В. Гормональные изменения в ответ на экстремальные факторы внешней среды.// Вестник РАМН. 2014; 9(10): 102—109.
10. Поленов А.Л. Общие принципы гипоталамической нейроэндокринной регуляции в защитно-приспособительных реакциях //В.Кн. эндокринная система организма и токсические факторы внешней среды.Л.1980,с272-285.
11. Саркисов Д.С.,и соавт., Морфология компенсаторно – приспособительных процессов //М.,ВИНИТИ.,1983, 135с.
12. Ташкэ К., Введение в количественную и цито-гистологическую морфологию.// Изд. Румыня.1980.с.10-22.

13. Хесин Я.Е.,Размеры ядра и функциональные состояние клеток.М.,1967,с 423.
14. Якимов И. А, Логинова Е. С. Анализ изменений уровня гормонов щитовидной железы при некоторых видах смерти.//Журн: Альманах современной науки и образования. 2017;(6): 91-92.
15. Bhasin, S. Testosterone therapy in men with hypogonadism / S. Bhasin, J.P. Brito, G.R. Cunningham et al. // An Endocrine Society clinical practice guideline. J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.2018;(103):1715–1744.
16. Garcia-Segura L. M, Azcoitia I., DonCarlos L. L. Neuroprotection by estradiol. Progress in Neurobiology 2001; 63 (1): 29—60.
17. Hernández-Hernández, J.M. Kisspeptin Stimulatestion of Luteinizing Hormone (LH) during Postpartum Anestrus Continuous and Restricted Suckling / J.M. Hernández-Hernández Becerril-érez et al. // Animals (Basel). 2021;(11):1-8.
18. Karabaev A.G. et al. Reactivity of the supraoptic, arcuate nucleus of the hypothalamus and the B-and D-basophilic cells of the adenohipophysis in the early postreanimation period. //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. 2021;8 (3): 954-957.
19. Karabaev A.G. Relationship between the reactivity of the autonomic nervous system and the morphofunctional activity of basophilic cells of the adenohipophysis in the post-resuscitation period. // Science and World International scientific journal 2020; 3 (79):55-62.
20. Karabayev A. G., R. I. Isroilov. Morphofunctional Changes in Basophilic Cells of the denohipophysis during Post-resuscitation Disease // Journal of Advances in Medicine and Medical Research 2020;32 (8):130-135.
21. Mirone, V. European Association of Urology Position Statement on the role of the urologist in the management of male hypogonadism and

testosterone therapy / V. Mirone, F. Debruyne, G. Dohle et al. // Eur. Urol. 2017;(72):164–167.

22. Mulhall, J.P. Evaluation and management of testosterone deficiency / J.P. Mulhall, L.W. Trost, R.E. Brannigan // AUA guideline. J. Urol. 2018;(200): 423–432.

23. Oberbeck R., Dahlweid M., Koch R. et al. Dehydroepiandrosterone decreases mortality rate and improves cellular immune function during polymicrobial sepsis. Crit. Care Med. 2001; 29 (2): 380-384.

24. Pierce B.N., Clarke I.J., Turner A.I., Rivalland E.T., Tilbrook A.J. Cortisol disrupts the ability of estradiol-17 β to induce the LH surge in ovariectomized ewes. Domest. Anim. Endocrinol. 2009; 36 (4):202–208.

25. Roof R. L, Hall E. D. Gender differences in acute CNS trauma and stroke: neuroprotective effects of estrogen and progesterone. J. Neurotrauma 2000; 17 (5): 367—388.